

Research Article

Independent Character in Online Learning on Student Learning Outcomes

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Received: June 08, 2024

Accepted: June 27, 2024

Published: July 05, 2024

Abstract

This research aims to identify the effect of applying independent character in online learning, especially in Civics subjects, on student learning outcomes. This research is ex post facto research with a quantitative approach to see the influence of independent character in online learning. This research was conducted at SMK Negeri 2 Salatiga. The data in this research was obtained from questionnaires and documentation in the form of student learning outcomes. The instrument was validated using content validation and construct validity tests. The reliability test in this research was carried out using Cronbach's alpha. The data analysis techniques used in this research are simple linear regression analysis and difference tests. The results of this research show that there is a significant influence of independent character on learning in the Pancasila and Citizenship Education subject network on the learning outcomes of classroom students. This is indicated by a significance value (sig.) of 0.000 which is less than the probability of 0.05. The R square value in class with the influence of independent character on good student learning outcomes, strengthening independent character must be one of the main focuses in the learning process. Strengthening independent character in online learning not only helps students to remain productive during the pandemic, but also prepares them to face future learning challenges better.

Keywords: Independent Character, Online Learning, Learning Results.

Introduction

Education is the main milestone in developing a country. This is in line with Idris, *et al.*, (2012: 443) which states that education is a milestone in the development of a nation by providing knowledge and skills to shape the personality of the younger generation. The importance of emphasizing education in creating skilled and knowledgeable individuals, will contribute a lot to the overall development and progress of the country. With a strong education, the younger generation can grow into leaders with integrity, innovation and the ability to face global challenges. A good education not only provides technical knowledge and skills, but also develops character, ethics, and critical thinking skills. This enables the younger generation to make wise decisions, adapt to change, and make positive contributions to society and the country. Especially now in the era of globalization, the ability to think creatively, innovatively, independently and solve problems effectively is becoming increasingly important, and holistic education is the key to achieving this. The hope of implementing education is that someone can know and understand various knowledge and be able to develop themselves, increase productivity, and establish social harmony that can be useful in social life. Education plays an important role in opening individuals' horizons, providing the skills needed to compete in the world of work, and helping in the formation of good character. With education, individuals not only learn to fulfill personal needs, but also learn to contribute positively to society, create a harmonious and productive environment, and strengthen social ties that support mutual progress.

The Indonesian government has the responsibility to implement good education, and there are many efforts made by the government to implement good education, including making various regulations and policies related to the implementation of education, namely through Law (UU) no. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, which states that the function of national education is to develop abilities and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in order to make the nation's life more intelligent. Through this law, the government is committed to providing an education system that does not only focus on

academic aspects, but also on developing character and strong moral values. In this way, it is hoped that education in Indonesia can produce a generation that is intelligent, has integrity and is able to contribute to the development of a dignified civilization. This policy also emphasizes the importance of education in preparing individuals to play an active role in society, as well as supporting the creation of a just, prosperous and civilized society. This is also supported by Dirgantoro (2016: 2-3) who states that there is a government mandate to form people who are intelligent and have character, so that a generation will be born with character that breathes the noble values of the nation and religion. Dirgantoro emphasized the importance of the government's role in creating a holistic education system, which not only prioritizes intellectual aspects but also moral and spiritual aspects. Thus, education in Indonesia aims to create individuals who not only have the knowledge and skills necessary to compete at the global level, but also have integrity, ethics and commitment to national and religious values. This generation is expected to be able to become leaders who contribute positively to the development of the country and are able to maintain unity and harmony in a multicultural society.

One of the strategies and efforts made by the government in preparing quality human resources is to create a character education strengthening program. Presidential Regulation (Perpres) no. 87 of 2017 concerning Strengthening Character Education which was later strengthened by Minister of Education and Culture Regulation (Permendikbud) No. 20 of 2018 concerning Strengthening Character Education in Formal Education Units contains the PPK (Strengthening Character Education) program. Apart from that, currently there is also a government program to strengthen the profile of Pancasila students which is being implemented in schools. This program aims to internalize the values of Pancasila in students, so that they can grow into individuals with strong character, integrity and national insight. Strengthening the Pancasila student profile includes six main aspects, namely: (1) Faith, devotion to God Almighty, and noble character, which means developing students' spirituality and morality. (2) Global diversity, which means fostering mutual respect and tolerance in a multicultural society. (3) Working together, which means encouraging cooperation and social care. (4) Independent, which means building independence and responsibility. (5) Critical reasoning, which means developing critical and analytical thinking skills. (6) Creative, which means encouraging innovation and creativity. By implementing these programs, the government is trying to ensure that education does not only focus on cognitive aspects, but also on developing character and noble values which are a strong foundation for nation building. It is hoped that this will produce a young generation who is ready to face future challenges with integrity, expertise and high national spirit. This indicates that independent character is an important character that must always be strengthened in students, especially when the COVID-19 pandemic occurred in various countries which made the implementation of education in schools experience obstacles. Many schools have been closed in an effort to contain the spread of the COVID-19 virus. The COVID-19 pandemic has changed the global education landscape drastically by encouraging the adoption of online learning as the main solution to continue the teaching and learning process amidst social and physical restrictions. Online learning or online learning has become the main choice for many schools and universities as a response to this emergency situation. By utilizing information and communication technology, online learning allows students to access learning materials, interact with teachers, and participate in teaching and learning activities without having to be in a physical classroom. With the necessity of online learning, independent character begins to develop among students because they are used to learning independently. Online learning forces them to manage time, understand material, and complete assignments without direct classroom interaction. This involves the ability to set clear learning goals, design effective learning strategies, and evaluate their own learning progress.

In addition, online learning encourages students to be more proactive in seeking additional information and solving problems on their own, such as technical problems with internet connections or using learning platforms that are new to them. This strengthens characteristics such as perseverance, independence, and responsibility in the learning process. These independent learning experiences are not only relevant during the pandemic, but also provide valuable skills for facing future challenges. The ability to learn independently will provide long-term benefits by developing problem-solving, creativity and perseverance skills that are important in their lives and careers going forward. Thus, although online learning began as a response to an emergency, the independent character that students develop in this process can become a solid foundation for their future personal and academic growth. In Kusuma's research (2020: 169) it was stated that the application of online learning had a positive impact on student learning independence during distance education. This was confirmed by Makur *et al.*, (2021: 10) which states that 70% of students have demonstrated an independent character in learning by setting goals, strategies, managing time, and carrying out self-evaluation in terms of learning. Independence also plays an important role in increasing students' fighting power, so that they have strong motivation to continue learning and developing even though they

face various obstacles. In addition, a high attitude of responsibility and initiative will help students to be more proactive in seeking the information and learning resources they need, as well as being more confident in overcoming various learning problems. The independent character in learning possessed by students can also help students to improve learning achievement. The results of previous research conducted by Ferazona and Suryanti (2020: 108) stated that the cognitive learning outcomes of students through online learning showed very good results with a percentage of 53.33%. Independent character plays an important role in this situation because it allows students to remain enthusiastic and motivated in learning even though they have to do it independently. By having an attitude of responsibility, initiative, and self-confidence, students can organize their own learning strategies, manage time effectively, and self-evaluate their learning progress. This helps them to stay focused and committed to their learning goals even without direct supervision from the teacher. Apart from that, high learning motivation also encourages students to look for various additional learning sources outside the material provided by the teacher, thereby enriching their understanding and skills. The use of technology in online learning also opens up access to various sources of information and knowledge that students can utilize to improve their learning achievements. Therefore, strengthening independent character must be one of the main focuses in the learning process. Strengthening independent character in online learning not only helps students to remain productive during the pandemic, but also prepares them to face learning challenges in the future better.

Research Method

This research is ex-post facto research with a quantitative approach. Ex-post facto research is intended to examine cause-and-effect relationships that are not manipulated or treated by researchers. Causal research is carried out on programs, activities or events that are taking place or have occurred. The research was conducted when students had participated in online learning. This research aims to identify the influence of the independent character of online learning on student learning outcomes in vocational high schools. The location chosen for this research was SMK Negeri 2 Salatiga. The population in this study was all level X students, totaling 642 students. The sample in this study was level X students who were then selected using a simple random sampling technique. Data collection techniques and instruments use questionnaires and documentation. Instrument validity and reliability uses content validity, construct validity, and instrument reliability. Meanwhile, the data analysis techniques used in this research are descriptive analysis and simple linear regression test analysis and difference test analysis.

Research Results and Discussion

Character education applied in every educational environment is a deliberate effort to build the character of students at school (Berkowitz and Hoppe, 2009: 132; Kamaruddin, 2012: 225; James, *et al.*, 2014: 8). The Indonesian government has taken steps by issuing a policy of implementing character education at all levels of education, from elementary school to tertiary institutions, through Presidential Regulation (PP) No 87 of 2017 concerning Strengthening Character Education (PPK), which is then supported by a Regulation of the Ministry of Education and Culture (Permendikbud) No. 20 of 2018. This PPK program is designed as a step to improve the character formation of students. The implementation of strengthening character education in schools can be done in the classroom by integrating character into subjects. This approach is in line with the views of Hendarman *et al.*, (2017: 35-42) which states that class-based PPK can be implemented by integrating character into the learning process in the classroom.

Moreover, currently, there is a program to strengthen the profile of Pancasila students to strengthen the character of students. By integrating character education into the curriculum, schools can create a learning environment that supports the moral and ethical development of students. This includes teaching values such as honesty, responsibility, discipline, cooperation and tolerance, which are expected to shape students into individuals with morals and good character. Practically, the integration of character in learning can be done through various methods, such as class discussions about the moral values contained in the lesson material, group projects that encourage cooperation and responsibility, and assessments that also consider aspects of character. Thus, character education is not just an additional task, but an inseparable part of the entire educational process at school. Through this approach, it is hoped that students will not only gain adequate academic knowledge, but also become individuals who have strong character and are ready to face future challenges with positive attitudes and behavior.

Some time ago, the COVID-19 pandemic has hampered various sectors in the education sector. The Indonesian government responded by issuing regulations regarding online learning through a circular letter from the Ministry of Education and Culture which regulates education policies in the emergency situation of the spread of the COVID-19 virus. Sadikin and Hamidah (2020: 215) emphasized that the main solution in

dealing with the pandemic is online learning, which is the basis for the government to support its implementation. In this context, students are needed to develop strong independent character. The opinion of Kusumadewi *et al.*, (2020: 12) supports that the important character in online learning is the independent character, where students are expected to be able to complete their own tasks and obligations without relying on the help of others. The first step in developing this independent character is to form an attitude of independence in learning, where students learn not to depend on other people. Efforts to increase students' independence can be done by periodically providing assignments that must be done independently (Somawati, 2016: 37).

This independent character development is in line with the Pancasila student profile strengthening program which is currently being implemented to strengthen student character. By integrating character education into the curriculum, schools can create a learning environment that supports the moral and ethical development of students. This includes teaching values such as honesty, responsibility, discipline, cooperation and tolerance, which are expected to shape students into individuals with morals and good character. Practically, the integration of character in learning can be done through various methods, such as class discussions about the moral values contained in the lesson material, group projects that encourage cooperation and responsibility, and assessments that also consider aspects of character. Thus, character education is not just an additional task, but an inseparable part of the entire educational process at school. Through this approach, it is hoped that students will not only gain adequate academic knowledge, but also become individuals who have strong character and are ready to face future challenges with positive attitudes and behavior. The integration of character education, especially independent character, in online learning is very important to ensure students remain productive during the pandemic and prepare them to better face learning challenges in the future.

Students' independence is also reflected in their behavior during the learning process. The difference between students who have high independence in learning and those who are less independent can be observed in the way they face challenges and complete learning tasks. Independent students tend to be more proactive in finding solutions, more disciplined in managing their time, and more responsible for their learning outcomes. Conversely, students who are less independent may more often require additional guidance, be less organized, and be less able to complete assignments effectively without external assistance. In the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic which forces the implementation of online learning, independent character development is a crucial aspect in the education process to ensure students can continue to learn effectively and independently even in unusual situations like this. Online learning requires students to be more independent in managing study time, overcoming technological obstacles, and understanding subject matter without intensive face-to-face interaction with teachers. The subject that plays a crucial role in forming students' independent character in online learning is Pancasila and Citizenship Education (PPKn). This education has an important aim in instilling character in the school environment, as expressed by Rahayu (2017: 1).

Citizenship education is expected to be able to develop students' values, morals and behavior. Pancasila and Citizenship Education is a typical term for citizenship education in Indonesia, the focus of which is on developing attitudes and abilities to defend the country, especially on cognitive and affective aspects (attitude/personality). Arif's opinion (2020: 3) also supports this by stating that through Pancasila and Citizenship Education, it is hoped that it can become a means of developing a dignified national character. Citizenship education has three main components, namely civic knowledge, civic skills and civic character (civic dispositions) (Branson, 1999: 8). This means that citizenship education is tasked with developing these three aspects of ability in students, so that they can become smart and good citizens. By integrating character education into the curriculum, schools can create a learning environment that supports the moral and ethical development of students. This includes teaching values such as honesty, responsibility, discipline, cooperation and tolerance, which are expected to shape students into individuals with morals and good character. Practically, the integration of character in learning can be done through various methods, such as class discussions about the moral values contained in the lesson material, group projects that encourage cooperation and responsibility, and assessments that also consider aspects of character. Thus, character education is not just an additional task, but an inseparable part of the entire educational process at school. Through this approach, it is hoped that students will not only gain adequate academic knowledge, but also become individuals who have strong character and are ready to face future challenges with positive attitudes and behavior. The integration of character education, especially independent character, in online learning is very important to ensure students remain productive during the pandemic and prepare them to better face learning challenges in the future. Students who take part in online learning on Pancasila and Citizenship

Education (PPKn) subjects well will help to form an independent character within themselves which will have an effect on improving academic achievement. Based on the results of data analysis using questionnaires and documentation of student learning outcomes, there is a positive influence of students' independent character in online learning on their learning outcomes.

Table 1. Simple linear regression test.

Model		Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	61.345	3.865		15.873	.000
	Independence	.283	.049	.565	5.735	.000

Based on Table 1, the regression coefficient value is (+), so it can be concluded that the independent character in online learning (X) has a positive effect on the learning outcomes of class X Industrial students (Y). The regression equation is $Y = 61.345 + 0.283X$. Meanwhile, to ascertain whether the regression coefficient is significant or not (in the sense that variable X has an effect on variable Y) a hypothesis test can be carried out by comparing the significance value with a probability of 0.05. The basis for decision making is if the significance value (Sig.) is less than 0.05 probability, which means that there is an influence of independent character in online learning (X) on learning outcomes (Y).

Table 2. Hypothesis test and t test.

Class	Sign value hypothesis test	R square values	Large influence
X	0.000	0.320	32 %

Based on Table 1 and Table 2, it shows that the significance (Sig.) result of 0.000 is less than <probability 0.05. This shows that H0 is rejected or there is an influence of the character of independence on the learning outcomes of class t table, then there is an influence of independent character in online learning on the learning outcomes of class = 70. Looking at the distribution table of t table values with df 70, the result is 1.66691. So with the calculated t value of 5.735 greater than > t table of 1.66691, it can be concluded that H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted, meaning that there is an influence of independent character in online learning on student learning outcomes. After knowing the influence, we then looked at the magnitude of the influence of the independent character in online learning on the learning outcomes of class X industrial students. Based on table 1, the magnitude of the influence of independent character in online learning on the results of class X students at SMK Negeri 2 Salatiga can be seen from the R square value. These results mean that the influence of the character of independence on the learning outcomes of class X vocational school students is 32%, while the remaining 68% is influenced by other variables not studied.

Pattaro's opinion (2016: 25) supports this finding, stating that a character education approach that is applied strictly and with a scientific basis can facilitate an effective learning process. Character education can have a positive effect on prosocial values and academic achievement and can reduce risky behavior. Thus, students who try to follow the teacher's directions to form independent character in online learning will have an impact on good learning outcomes. The opinion of Parker *et al.*, (2010: 817) also supports this, stating that behavioral involvement during academic activities can be seen as an indicator of cognitive and emotional involvement that leads to increased academic achievement. This engagement reflects how students overcome academic challenges, manage time, and take responsibility for their own learning. Practically, to develop independent character in online learning, teachers can provide tasks that must be completed independently and encourage students to find their own solutions before asking for help. Class discussions about the importance of independence, group projects that encourage cooperation and responsibility, and assessments that consider aspects of character are some methods that can be used.

By integrating character education, especially independent character, in the curriculum, schools can create a learning environment that supports the moral and ethical development of students. Strong character education will help students not only gain academic knowledge but also form individuals who have strong character and are ready to face future challenges with positive attitudes and behavior. The integration of character education in online learning is very important to ensure students remain productive during the pandemic and prepare them to better face future learning challenges. This means that students having good independent character in implementing online learning can support students' success in the field of academic achievement. This is also supported by research conducted by Zurqoni, *et al.*, (2018: 882) which states that the aim of character education is also to support the success of students, both in academic and social life. Holstein (1986:26) also strengthens this by stating that independence has a very important role in

teaching and learning activities. Independence allows students to participate in the learning process actively and creatively.

Teachers can assess academic achievement through student learning outcomes in online learning. This is in line with the opinion of Sudijono (2012: 32) who states that learning outcomes are an evaluation action that can reveal aspects of the thinking process, aspects of values or attitudes and aspects of skills inherent in each individual student. By carrying out an assessment, a teacher will then be able to evaluate various things that students lack, so that various constructive input can be given so that they can be maximized again to get a better quality of education. Learning evaluation does not only target the availability or unavailability of sophisticated applications for online learning, but the planning, implementation and constraints of teachers and students must be part of the overall evaluation (Waruwu, 2020: 291). This is confirmed by the opinion of Briekerhoff (1986: 9) who states that evaluation is a process that determines the extent to which educational goals can be achieved. Online learning provides effective learning methods by utilizing various technologies, such as related feedback, collaboration between group activities and independent learning, as well as personalization of learning based on individual needs, including the use of simulations and games (Ghirardini, 2011: 120). In the context of online learning for Pancasila and Citizenship Education (PPKn) subjects, the results of the questionnaire show that the independent character of class X students has an average score of 77.70% in the good category. This shows that students are able to develop their independent character in the context of online learning.

It is hoped that developing independent character through this learning can equip students to become independent in facing various challenges. This view is in line with research by Susanto (2017: 3), which emphasizes the importance of education that does not only focus on academic aspects but also on life skills which include independent character. In this way, it is hoped that students' knowledge, abilities, skills and independence can increase, providing provisions for success in the world of work or in becoming professionals. In this research, there are five independent character indicators used, namely fighting power, self-assessment, responsibility, initiative, and courage (self-confidence). These five indicators help measure the extent to which students are able to demonstrate independent character in the online learning process. Fighting power reflects students' ability to remain persistent in facing learning challenges. Self-assessment refers to students' ability to evaluate themselves objectively. Responsible shows a responsible attitude in completing academic tasks. Initiative shows students' willingness to take steps without having to be asked first. Meanwhile, courage or self-confidence reflects students' belief in their own abilities to face challenges. Through measuring and developing these indicators, independent character education in online learning can make a significant contribution to students' personal and academic development. Thus, schools can play an important role in forming individuals who not only excel in academics but also have strong character and are ready to face the competitive world of work.

Fighting power is an important indicator of independent character. Poerwopoespito and Utomo (2010: 185) emphasize that independence has a crucial meaning in forming a strong person. Students who have high fighting power tend to be capable and resilient in facing various challenges and difficulties. When applied in the context of online learning, students who have high fighting spirit will have a strong fighting spirit to achieve satisfactory learning results. Stoltz's opinion (2000: 38) also supports this idea by stating that success is achieved when someone can continue to progress towards their goals, even though they are faced with various obstacles or difficulties. In other words, students who have good independent character, including high fighting power, will always have the personal resilience to overcome challenges and difficulties in the learning process. They do not give up easily or are influenced by obstacles that arise along the way. In the educational context, online learning demands perseverance and a strong fighting spirit from students. High fighting spirit allows them to remain focused, persistent, and make maximum effort in achieving their academic goals, even in learning situations that may be unusual or full of challenges. Therefore, developing independent character, including fighting power, has a very important role in preparing students to face various situations and pursue success with firm determination. Fighting power has such a big role in daily life that it can increase work productivity which in the end can realize organizational citizenship behavior. Students with high fighting power will be able to use various methods to get good results in implementing online learning, one of which is by organizing learning methods. Organizing how students learn can be done by making a learning activity plan.

Students who have high fighting power will always take part in online learning by arriving on time so they don't miss out on material, indicating that these students have good fighting power. This is supported by the opinion of Lestari (2014: 115) who states that fighting power is a conceptual framework that is able to

predict how far a person is able to overcome problems/difficulties in his life. Students with high fighting power will know the difficulties they will encounter if they do not arrive on time for learning. Students' fighting spirit also plays an important role in students' success in the academic field. With high enthusiasm, students will have a strong determination to succeed in learning. Ryan and Deci (2006: 1562) in their theory of self-determination states that humans have the urge within themselves to fight, so that they can improve their personality and regulation. Students will continue to try to be able to control and direct themselves while remaining focused on the goals they want to achieve. An example of an application that should be carried out by students regarding assignments is that if the time used to complete the work is not enough, then students will continue to try to complete the assignment so that the work can still be completed on time. Apart from that, students will continue to try to direct themselves to do assignments on the same day so that assignments do not pile up and the work can be done optimally.

Increasing students' learning competence can be improved through an effective learning process using various learning resources. Using a variety of learning resources in the learning process can have a positive influence on students' learning outcomes (Zakaria, 2007). Students who have high fighting power will independently explore other learning sources as an addition to carrying out learning. This is supported by research by Supriyadi (2015: 136) which states that independent interaction is a pattern of interaction between students and learning resources where students actively interact independently with learning resources. Learning will be more meaningful when students are able to explore their own abilities, which will make students more creative and free to explore (independently) according to the learning material. The independent character of students can be seen from the students' self-assessment attitude. Self-concept is the result of how a person sees, feels and wants himself (Hardjana, 2003: 96). This is supported by the opinion of Desmita (2014: 164) who states that self-concept is an idea about oneself which includes beliefs, views and assessments of oneself. Students in implementing online learning are required to learn independently. Assignments given by teachers in online learning are always intended as individual assignments. This can train students to assess themselves to be able to participate in online learning well, by not basing themselves on other people and trying to always act or think to complete the tasks given according to their heart's wishes. Self-assessment carried out by students can help build self-confidence so that they are able to be independent in the current online learning environment. This is reinforced by the opinion of Burns (1993: 18) that a positive self-concept can help someone to increase self-confidence so that it can motivate someone to be even better.

Responsibility is an indicator of independent character. Responsibility is a person's attitude and behavior to carry out their duties and obligations that must be carried out towards themselves, society and the environment. When it comes to implementing online learning, students have the duty and obligation to participate in online learning as well as possible. Students who always try to complete the work given and always try to correct the work before it is submitted so that it complies with the provisions and steps that have been determined show that the individual's attitude of responsibility is very strong. Yaumi (2014:114) states that responsibility is the obligation to carry out and complete tasks assigned by someone so that they must always be fulfilled because they have punitive consequences if they are not carried out. This means that when students do not complete the responsibilities given properly, they must always be responsible for accepting the consequences/punishments that have been previously agreed upon. Therefore, responsibility for completing assigned tasks and the obligation to correct work in accordance with the provisions that have been given is one form of responsibility that students must always have. Students must always understand the consequences if they do not carry out the tasks they have been given. Various weaknesses and deficiencies in online learning can make students discouraged from participating in online learning. However, students who have strong responsibility can overcome various problems that occur in online learning activities. This is supported by the opinion of Tasmara (1995: 73) who assumes that responsibility is work that must be done with perseverance and sincerity. This means that, no matter how many obstacles they face, students must remain responsible for carrying out online learning. The thing that is used as input is that students must continue to try to adapt to online learning. Students can review how to learn in online learning to find out solutions to the problems they face.

The fourth sub-indicator of independent character is initiative. Initiative can be interpreted as an attitude that is created because of an urge or desire within a person to do something. Elisabeth, *et al.*, (2009: 46) stated that student initiative will have a positive influence. Students with a strong independent character will have the initiative to learn on their own without any coercion from anywhere. Students who have the initiative to complete practice questions in textbooks or study material before being assigned by the teacher are a form of independent character in learning. Learning independently is a form of independence, students

are required to have their own activeness and initiative in learning. Students with a high level of initiative will participate more in learning activities so they are able to solve problems easily. Students with high initiative will be able to come up with many new ideas as a form of student participation in online learning. Some things that need to be improved in students are the initiative to come up with new ideas in online learning, and trying to complete practice questions in the textbook or study material for the next meeting before being assigned by the teacher. If these things are implemented optimally, a good initiative attitude will be formed in students, so that through good initiative they can form students' independent character in carrying out online learning.

Self-confidence is the final indicator of independent character. Self-confidence is an individual's ability to understand and believe in all his potential so that he can use it in adapting to his living environment (Dariyo, 2007: 10). With strong self-confidence, students can believe in the strengths that exist within themselves and this belief makes them feel capable of achieving the goals they want to achieve. Hakim (2002: 122) states that students' self-confidence in the school environment can be built through various forms of activities, one of which is cultivating the courage to ask questions. One form of strong student self-confidence is having the courage to ask questions in learning. The independence that students have is to foster a sense of self-confidence which is very important for students so that in implementing learning, students are faster in receiving learning material. If students are quicker to accept and understand the material provided, this will affect the teacher's assessment which will ultimately affect student learning outcomes. Self-confidence is an attitude or belief in one's own abilities so that one is not too anxious in one's actions, feels free to do things according to one's wishes and is responsible for one's actions, is polite in interacting with other people (Lauster, 2003: 4). Dare to express opinions that are different from other people's opinions and dare to answer questions given by other people is a form of self-confidence that must be developed in students. With the positive influence of independent character on student learning outcomes, strengthening independent character must be a top priority in the learning process. This is not only relevant to maintaining student productivity during the pandemic, but also to better prepare them to face future learning challenges. Online learning has proven itself to be an effective method for building independent character, because it requires students to manage time, learn independently, and overcome various obstacles that may arise. In this context, strengthening independent character not only has an impact on academic achievement, but also on students' ability to develop independence, perseverance and enthusiasm in achieving their learning goals. Thus, through education that focuses on developing independent character, students will be better prepared mentally and emotionally to face changes and challenges in the world of education and professional life in the future.

Conclusions

Based on the description of the research results and discussions related to the analysis of students' independent character in learning in the network of Pancasila and Citizenship Education subjects at SMK Negeri 2 Salatiga, it can be concluded that the independent character in learning in the PPKn subject network has a significant influence on learning outcomes learners. This is indicated by the significance (Sig.) result of the hypothesis test of 0.000 which is less than <probability 0.05, meaning that H_0 is rejected so that there is an influence of independent character on student learning outcomes. The magnitude of the influence of independent character in online learning on student outcomes can be seen from the R square value which shows 0.320, meaning that the magnitude of the influence is 32% and the remainder is influenced by other variables not explained in this research. The quality of students' independent character in online learning for Civics subjects also shows that they are in the good category with an average percentage of 77.70%, while for student learning outcomes it shows that 100% of students get complete learning results that exceed the school's KKM, which is 72. With this the positive influence of independent character on students' learning outcomes, strengthening independent character must be one of the main focuses in the learning process. Independent character includes aspects such as fighting power, self-assessment, responsibility, initiative and self-confidence, all of which play an important role in supporting students' academic success and social life.

Strengthening independent character in online learning provides various significant benefits for a better learning process in the future. First, this helps students to remain productive even though learning is carried out online. With a strong independent character, students can manage their time better, develop independent learning abilities, and complete assignments effectively even without direct supervision from the teacher. Second, strengthening independent character prepares students to face learning challenges in the future. And in the current digital era and rapidly developing information, the ability to learn independently that is gained during online learning is very useful. Students who have a strong independent character will be better able to navigate various learning situations, both in formal and non-formal education

contexts. They will be better prepared to face challenges in the world of work and everyday life, where lifelong learning skills are becoming increasingly relevant. Therefore, focusing on strengthening independent character in online learning must be a priority. This can be done through learning strategies that encourage active participation, provide constructive feedback, and provide opportunities for students to develop their initiative and responsibility. In this way, students not only achieve good learning results, but also grow into individuals who are independent, confident, and ready to face the future with all its challenges.

Declarations

Acknowledgments: Special thanks are expressed to Samsuri as a Lecturer in Citizenship Education at Yogyakarta State University and a teacher at SMK N 2 Salatiga who has helped the author in writing this paper.

Author Contributions: Both authors contributed to the conception and design of the work, drafted the manuscript, revised it critically for important intellectual content, gave final approval to the version to be published and agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Consent to Publish: The authors agree to publish the paper in the International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research.

Data Availability Statement: The data sets used or analyzed during this research are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Research Content: The research content of manuscript is original and has not been published elsewhere.

References

1. Arif, D.B. 2020. Citizenship education for building national character (prospects and challenges in a multicultural society). Conference or Workshop: PPKn FKIP Study Program, Ahmad Dahlan University, 14 May 2012, Yogyakarta. Retrieved from <http://eprints.uad.ac.id/id/eprint/1771>
2. Berkowitz, M.W. and Hoppe, M.A. 2009. Character education and gifted children. *Journal of High Ability Studies*, 20(2): 131-142.
3. Branson, M.S. 1999. Learn civic education from America (Translation of Syarifudin, et al). Yogyakarta: LKIS.
4. Briekerhoff, R.O. et al. 1986. Program evaluation, a practitioner's guide for trainers and educationers. 4th Edition, Boston: Kluwer Nijboff Publishing.
5. Burns, R.B. 1993. Self-concept: Theory, measurement, judgment, and behavior (Translator: Eddy). Jakarta: Arcan.
6. Dariyo, A. 2007. Developmental psychology. Bandung: Refika Aditama.
7. Desmita. 2017. Psychology of student development. Bandung: Rosdakarya Youth.
8. Dirgantoro, A. 2016. The role of education in shaping national character in facing the Asean economic community (AEC) era. *PPKn Scientific Round Journal*, 2(1): 1-7.
9. Elisabeth, A.V.H., Jan, K.B.M., Janet, R.A.N. et al. 2009. Instructiveness of feedback during clerkships: Influence of supervisor, observation and student initiative. *Medical Teacher*, 31(1): 45-50.
10. Ferazona, S. and Suryanti. 2020. The influence of online learning on students' cognitive learning outcomes in limnology courses. *Journal of Research and Educational Chemistry*, 2(2): 102-110.
11. Ghirardini, B. 2011. E-learning methodologies. Germany: Federal Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Consumer Protection.
12. Hakim, T. 2002. Overcoming feelings of lack of self-confidence. Jakarta: Purwa Suara.
13. Hardjana, A.M. 2003. Intrapersonal and interpersonal communication. Yogyakarta: Kanisius.
14. Hendarman, H., Sayono, D., Supriyono, S. et al. 2017. Concepts and guidelines: Strengthening character education. Jakarta: Ministry of Education and Culture. Available at: <http://repositori.kemdikbud.go.id/id/eprint/30124>

15. Holstein, H. 1986. Students learn independently. Bandung: PT-Remadja Rosdakarya.
16. Idris, F., Hassan, Z., Ya'acob, A., et al. 2012. The role of education in shaping youth's national identity. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 59: 443-450.
17. James, A., Kristjansson, K., Walker, D.I. et al. 2014. Character education in UK schools. Birmingham: University of Birmingham.
18. Kamaruddin, S.A. 2012. Character education and students social behavior. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 6(4): 223-230.
19. Kusuma, D.A. 2020. The impact of implementing online learning on students' self-regulated learning in geometry courses during distance learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. *Theorem: Mathematics Theory and Research*, 5(2): 169-175.
20. Kusumadewi, R.F., Yustiana, S. and Nasihah, K. 2020. Fostering student independence during online learning as a result of Covid-19 in elementary schools. *JRPD: Journal of Basic Education Research*, 1(1): 7-13.
21. Lauster, P. 2003. Personality test (Translation: Gulo, D.H.). Jakarta: PT-Literary Earth.
22. Lestari, E. 2014. The relationship between future orientation and fighting power in class XII students at SMA Negeri 12 North Samarinda. *E-Journal of Psychology*, 2(3): 314-326.
23. Makur, A.P., Jehadus, E., Fedi, S., Jelatu, S., Murni, V. and Raga, P. 2021. Student learning independence in distance learning during the pandemic. *Mosharafa: Journal of Mathematics Education*, 10(1): 1-12.
24. Parker, D.C., Nelson, J.S. and Burns, M.K. 2010. Comparison of correlates of classroom behavior problems in schools with and without a school-wide character education program. *Psychology in the Schools*, 47(8): 817-827.
25. Pattaro, C. 2016. Character education: Themes and research-an academic literature review. *Italian Journal of Sociology of Education*, 8(1): 5-30.
26. Poerwopoespito, O.S. and Utomo, T. 2010. Overcoming the human crisis in the company. Jakarta: Grasindo.
27. Rahayu, A.S. 2017. Pancasila and citizenship education. Jakarta: Bumi Literacy.
28. Ryan, R.M. and Deci, E.L. 2006. Self-regulation and the problem of human autonomy: Does psychology need choice, self-determination, and will?. *Journal of Personality*, 74(6): 1557-1586.
29. Sadikin, A. and Hamidah, A. 2020. Online learning in the midst of the Covid-19 outbreak. *Biodik: Scientific Journal of Biology Education*, 6(2): 214-224.
30. Somawati. 2016. The influence of anxiety and learning independence on the mathematical communication skills of state vocational school students in Pasar Rebo sub-district. *Research and Development Journal of Education*, 3(1): 35-51.
31. Stoltz, P.G. 2000. Adversity quotient: Turning barriers into opportunities (Translation: Hermaya, T.). Jakarta: Grasindo.
32. Sudijono, A. 2012. Introduction to educational evaluation. Jakarta: PT-RajaGrafindo Persada.
33. Supriyadi, S. 2015. Utilization of learning resources in the learning process. *Lanthanide Journal*, 3(2): 127-139.
34. Susanto, T.Y. 2017. Independent character education for Brilian Banyumas village cadre education students. Thesis: Semarang State University.
35. Tasmara, T. 1995. Cultivate an Islamic work ethic. Jakarta: Gema Human.
36. Waruwu, M. 2020. Evaluative study of the implementation of online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 27(2): 288-295.
37. Yaumi, M. 2014. Character education: Foundations, pillars, and implementation. Jakarta: Prenada Media Group.
38. Zakaria, E. 2007. Trends teaching and learning mathematics. Kuala Lumpur: Envoy Publications.

39. Zurqoni, Z., Retnawati, H., Apino, E. and Anazifa, R.D. 2018. Impact of character education implementation: A goal-free evaluation. *Problems of Education in the 21st Century*, 76(6): 881-899.

Citation: Anggriani Puspitaningrum and Samsuri. 2024. Independent Character in Online Learning on Student Learning Outcomes. *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research*, 8(7): 1-11.

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